

Title: Discovering patterns in exchange rate fluctuations

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INTRODUCTION:

Exchange rates are varying every hour with a considerable impact in the economic world. They are very important for markets, industries and businesses as they determine the levels of exports and imports in any country.

It is invaluable to know how exchange rates are evolving in time in order to make good decisions in any business. There are many difficulties in forecasting the exchange rates since its variations are influenced by many unpredictable events and factors that change over time such as differentials in inflation, public debt, terms of trade, political stability and economic performance, among others.

Exchange rates movements can have a significant impact on a company's returns. Multinational companies may see significant shifts in their profitability, as foreign exchange ("FX" "forex") rates may make locally held currency more valuable. Even local companies can be affected, as changing FX rates may substantially alter their material costs, or affect their ability to sell their goods in foreign countries at competitive prices (Wikinvest, 2016)

Data science, in particular some machine learning methods, can be used to tackle the problems of analyzing big amount of data about exchange rates of most important currencies, allowing the extraction of valuable knowledge for decision making

AIM:

To apply a method for mining association rules to discover patterns in data that allow to establish relations among the exchange rates fluctuations of most important currencies. The final result is a set of positive rules that shows the dependencies among the variations of exchange rates of selected currency pairs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

To do this work all the information was taken from OANDA, using an fxTrade Practice account to extract the data of exchange rates for each hour. OANDA is an award-winning Online Trading Platform, dedicated to support traders, allowing them full control of their trade strategies

For all stages of the process it was used RapidMiner Studio Basic 6.5. This tool provides the necessary functions to make the exploration and pre-processing of data as well as the data mining process. The data was integrated in one dataset using the R language, and then imported in RapidMiner

RESULTS:

Analyzing time series of exchange rate fluctuations (479 observations from January 3 to 29), the constant is the change. For EUR_CAD pair there are just few occurrences of values indicating that exchange rates remain constant in two continuous hours. A similar behavior is showed by the rest of currency pair fluctuations.

After applying Rapid Miner operators, with min confidence equal to 0.8, indicating that at least in 80% of cases the rules detected are true, the following association rules were obtained:

No.	Premises	Conclusion	Support	Confidence
1	USD_CAD, EUR_CAD	GBP_CAD	0.303	0.810
2	CAD_JPY	USD_JPY	0.355	0.833
3	EUR_GBP, EUR_CAD	EUR_USD	0.311	0.837
4	USD_JPY, CAD_JPY	GBP_JPY	0.303	0.853
5	EUR_CAD, GBP_CAD	USD_CAD	0.303	0.863
6	EUR_GBP, EUR_USD	EUR_CAD	0.311	0.866
7	USD_CAD, GBP_CAD	EUR_CAD	0.303	0.868
8	EUR_USD, EUR_CAD	EUR_GBP	0.311	0.871
9	USD_JPY, GBP_JPY	CAD_JPY	0.303	0.873
10	GBP_JPY, CAD_JPY	USD_JPY	0.303	0.912

The rule number ten with support 0.303 means that the premise or antecedent GBP_JPY, CAD_JPY appears 145 times in database (0.303×479). For that amount, the rule GBP_JPY, CAD_JPY => USD_JPY appears 132 times (0.912×145).

According to how were codified the fluctuations, rule number ten shows that every time exchange rates of GBP_JPY, CAD_JPY increase also do the same the pair USD_JPY, with the support and confidence before mentioned.

In general, statistics reveal GBP_JPY as the pair with the highest increment in one hour, having a value of 3.664, followed by USD_JPY (2.727) and EUR_JPY (2.517). The highest decrements correspond to GBP_JPY (-1.388), USD_JPY (-1.076) and EUR_JPY (-0.924). The pairs with the highest increments have the highest decrements.

It can be said that Euro currency exchange rates are the most influenced, appearing in four consequents. Euro is the currency with most probabilities to increase its value when other currencies increase its exchange rates. A deep analysis should be done to determine what rules don't provide extra knowledge in addition to other rules.

CONCLUSIONS:

This work can be developed for production systems using libraries in several programming languages, for example Weka in Java and the arules package in R. Of course, it has showed just the potential of the technique, for a better estimate it's important to use more than 479 transactions, so the rules can be considered significant from a statistical viewpoint. Also can be discovered negative association rules applying some other algorithms, which may enrich the knowledge to extract.

The rules don't establish cause-effect relations but only associations. They can be used for decision making in any business to anticipate the exchange rate fluctuations, having in hand some information on how exchange rates of premises will vary in few hours to determine the conclusions.

KEYWORDS:

Exchange rate fluctuations, Association rules, Data Mining

BIOGRAPHY:

I am graduated of Computer Science engineering, with nine years as professor of artificial intelligence at the university (UCI), with experience applying artificial intelligence techniques to obtain software products with better functionality to support the decision making in businesses. Following my passion for data, my current work consists in applying modern technologies to process big amount of data (Big Data), using tools like Hadoop, Spark, Hive, and to extract patterns and knowledge through machine learning techniques using Python and R. My training also includes statistics and math, the necessary knowledge to obtain accurate models for predictive and descriptive analysis of data.